

Enhancing Metadata for Inclusive Research on Entrenched Disadvantage

PROJECT FINAL REPORT

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1 PROJECT INFORMATION

INVESTMENT ID	https://doi.org/10.3565/X7VR-3532
PROJECT START AND END DATES	11/03/2024 - 30/09/2024
LEAD ORGANISATION	University of Queensland (UQ)
PARTNER ORGANISATIONS	Australian Bureau of Statistics Australian Research Data Commons Department of Education
PROJECT LEAD CONTACT PERSON	Professor Wojtek Tomaszewski
PROJECT MANAGER	Dr Denise Clague

1.1 Background

Australia is creating data systems, including public sector data assets, that can support research, policy analysis and evaluation in areas such as education, health, employment, inequality and disadvantage. However, the state of administrative data and the associated metadata needs to be improved so that considerably less time, effort and resources are required to conduct this research.

1.2 Achievement of project aims

This project aimed to showcase an example for enhancing metadata, based on the metadata associated with Higher Education (HE) administrative data within the Person Level Integrated Data Asset (PLIDA), formerly known as the Multi-Agency Data Integration Project (MADIP). The goal was to increase the data's utility for research analysts by focusing on metadata content, including good metadata practice, rather than on the technicalities surrounding information management or data quality itself.

The following work packages were undertaken in order to achieve the project aim.

Work Package 1: Review of best practice in metadata documentation for research analysts

- Work Package 1 (WP1) conducted a review of metadata needs relevant to research analysts and integrated administrative social science data (IASSD). This involved reviewing literature on metadata standards, data quality and IASSD, and identifying examples of effective metadata practice. The findings were documented in a WP1 Technical Report.

Work Package 2: Review of Higher Education metadata in PLIDA and its provenance

- Work Package 2 (WP2) assessed the current state of HE metadata within PLIDA and outside. This included reviewing available metadata, data dictionaries, and business rules. A WP2 Technical Report outlined deficiencies and areas for improvement.

Work Package 3: User experience consultations

- Work Package 3 (WP3) gathered feedback from users of HE data through targeted consultations. A WP3 Technical Report highlighted user experiences, issues with current metadata, and suggestions for improvement, contributing valuable insights for metadata enhancement.

Work Package 4: Solution design and forward plan

- Work Package 4 (WP4) designed solutions based on gap analysis from WP1-3 and developed a forward plan including guidelines for metadata standards.

Work Package 5: Developing a Monitoring and Evaluation plan to capture long-term outcomes

- Work Package 5 (WP5) developed an approach to measuring long-term outcomes, including program logic and performance indicators.

By systematically addressing each deliverable and leveraging insights from various work packages, the project aimed to significantly improve metadata quality and usability, ultimately enhancing the utility of HE administrative data for researchers and policymakers.

2 DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1. Achievements against project work packages/deliverables:

Use the following criteria and colours to assign a status to each work package:

Status Key

COMPLETED	Completed
NON-COMPLETION MAY IMPACT ON PROJECT OUTCOMES	Not yet completed and non-completion may have some impact on the project outcomes. Delay has been accepted by the Steering Committee and responsibility for completion has been assigned.
WILL NOT BE COMPLETED AND WILL IMPACT ON PROJECT OUTCOMES	Will not be completed and has an impact on the project outcomes. The Steering Committee has accepted the non-completion and understands the impact to the project outcomes.

DELIVERABLE / WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION (INCLUDE LINKS TO RELEVANT DOCUMENTATION)	AGREED DUE DATE	ACTUAL or EXPECTED COMPLETION DATE	STATUS
WP1.1	Definition of social science administrative data (in scope of project)	22/03/2024	22/03/2024	Completed
WP1.2	List of metadata standards and examples (in scope of project)	22/03/2024	22/03/2024	Completed
WP1.3	Steer Co sign off of Definition of social science administrative data (WP1.1) & List of metadata standards and examples (WP1.2)	29/03/2024	29/03/2024	Completed
WP1.4	WP1 Technical Report	13/06/2024	18/06/2024	Completed
WP1.5	Steer Co Sign off of WP1 Technical Report	14/06/2024	17/06/2024	Completed
WP2.1	Documentation of gaps in Higher Education metadata in PLIDA	26/04/2024	20/05/2024	Completed
WP2.2	Documentation of alternative sources of metadata based on Higher Education metadata available outside of PLIDA	10/05/2024	20/05/2024	Completed
WP2.3	Steer Co sign off of documentation of gaps in Higher Education metadata in PLIDA (WP2.1) and documentation of alternative sources of metadata based on Higher Education metadata available outside of PLIDA (WP2.2)	20/05/2024	20/05/2024	Completed

WP2.4	Consultations with data custodians/DoE	15/05/2024	15/05/2024	Completed
WP2.5	WP2 Technical Report	13/06/2024	18/06/2024	Completed
WP2.6	Steer Co Sign off of WP2 Technical Report (WP2.5)	15/06/2024	17/06/2024	Completed
WP3.1	Completed consultations with 8-10 users of HE Data in PLIDA	30/04/2024	13/05/2024	Completed
WP3.2	WP3 Technical Report	13/06/2024	18/06/2024	Completed
WP3.3	Steer Co Sign off of WP3 Technical Report (WP3.2)	15/06/2024	17/06/2024	Completed
WP4.1	Synthesis of findings from WP2-WP4 & gap analysis	15/07/2024	01/08/2024	Completed
WP4.2	Consultations with ABS and DoE on findings from WP2-WP4 & co-design a solution	31/07/2024	01/08/2024	Completed
WP4.3	Forward Plan on metadata with guidelines for ABS and data providers/custodians	28/08/2024	28/08/2024	Completed
WP4.4	WP4 Technical Report	28/08/2024	28/08/2024	Completed
WP4.5	Steer Co Sign off of Forward Plan (WP4.3) & WP4 Technical Report (WP4.4)	30/08/2024	30/08/2024	Completed
WP5.1	Develop draft program logic	15/07/2024	26/07/2024	Completed

WP5.2	Finalise the monitoring and evaluation plan	28/08/2024	28/08/2024	Completed
WP5.3	Steer Co Sign off of program logic (WP5.1) and monitoring and evaluation plan (WP5.2)	30/08/2024	30/08/2024	Completed

2.2. Project outputs

The major project outputs included:

- Metadata needs for research analysts in relation to integrated administrative social science data
- Good-practice metadata examples
- Assessment of existing metadata of HE admin data (within PLIDA/MADIP, and external to it).
- User experience report, based on targeted consultations, outlining perceived metadata shortcomings when working with PLIDA/MADIP/HE data and metadata user preferences.
- A forward plan with guidelines for improving PLIDA metadata .

Structure and Execution

- **Phase 1: Discovery Phase (March - June 2024)**
 - **WP1:** Reviewed metadata documentation needs for research analysts and produced a technical report.
 - **WP2:** Assessed existing HE metadata and produced a technical report on gaps and deficiencies.
 - **WP3:** Conducted user experience consultations to gather feedback and produce a report on user needs and issues.
- **Phase 2: Solution Design Phase (June - August 2024)**
 - **WP4:** Designed solutions based on gap analysis from WP1-3 and developed a forward plan including guidelines for PLIDA metadata improvements.
 - **WP5:** Developed an approach to monitoring long-term outcomes, including program logic and performance indicators.

2.3. Outreach and training activities

ACTIVITY	ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION	NO. OF PARTICIPANTS	DATE OF ACTIVITY
ABS ARDC Metadata Pilot presentation	ABS team members ran a 2 hour session with our project team to demonstrate the available ABS metadata and structure	Project team: 6 ABS: 3	04/04/2024
Consultations with users and data custodians/providers	Multiple consultations with data users and data providers/custodian's from UQ PBI, DoE, ABS	20 PLIDA users; 4 data providers/custodians	April/May 2024
ARDC HASS & I Symposium in Melbourne	Presentation on the Metadata pilot project	~ 60 attendees	14/06/2024
Social Sciences Week 2024 Webinar	A presentation on the Metadata Pilot project, and - potentially - some references to the new Social Science Research Infrastructure Network project	TBC - future event	10/09/2024
UQ Research and Innovation Week	A presentation on the Metadata Pilot project, and - potentially - some references to the new Social Science Research Infrastructure Network project	TBC - future event	1/10/2024

3 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

This pilot project laid the groundwork for a larger Social Sciences co-investment activity within the ARDC HASS&I RDC. This activity has been developed in line with the HASS & I RDC Co-Design Framework. Through open co-design workshops with a range of stakeholders, ARDC has confirmed the broader applicability of the problem statement identified in this pilot project, identified new project partners and designed a larger-scale activity directed at solving this problem, building on the findings of the pilot.

The current pilot project team has assisted in this co-design process by identifying new stakeholders to involve in co-design, sharing the pilot outcomes and lessons learned in the co-design sessions, and identifying new opportunities arising from the pilot project.

The Social Science Research Infrastructure Network project plan has been finalised and undergoing internal review by ARDC in preparation for submission to the ARDC Board meeting on 27 August.

5 PROJECT IMPACT

The ARDC and the Government wish to demonstrate the impact on researchers, industry and the general public of the NCRIS investment. Please complete the following sections as relevant to your program.

5.1 Impact stories

The pilot project has laid a crucial foundation for an upcoming, more extensive Social Sciences investment initiative within the ARDC HASS&I RDC – the Social Science Research Infrastructure Network. Building on the issues identified in this pilot project, and leveraging insights from open co-design workshops with a range of stakeholders, a large-scale project has been designed that includes new partners and a much more comprehensive program of work to tackle some of the most pressing challenges in the social science data infrastructure.

6 LESSONS LEARNED

6.1 What Went Well?

Positive lessons learned that can be beneficial when applied to other projects include:

- **Project planning:** The project plan was detailed enough to give visibility and help the project team stay on track and run to schedule. WP 1-3 were completed to enable WP 4-5 to be completed on time.
- **Collaboration:** Engaging with our project partners including ABS, ARDC and DoE provided important insights into relevant data and metadata sources. Timely inputs from them meant we were able to achieve what we planned to achieve by the end of the project.
- **Feedback:** The set up and role of the expert advisers and steering committee members was valuable for feedback and support.
- **Partnership building:** the partnerships built over the course of the pilot project – crucially with the ARDC and the ABS – have directly led to scoping a new, much more comprehensive and long-term project – Social Science Research Infrastructure Network.

6.2 What Could be Improved?

The project was scoped up over a relatively short time frame, following an accelerated co-design process.

The timeframe for project delivery was also very tight. This meant that there was little room to adjust deliverables, or the timeline specified in the project plan even when faced with unexpected difficulties, requiring close project management and frequent communication with project partners. Having more time to deliver the project would also enable a closer integration between the WPs, as they could be delivered in a more staggered timeline, rather than running concurrently.